

THEME "GENERAL METHODS OF UPBRINGING"

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Tashpulatova Khadicha

*Yeoju Technical Institute in Tashkent
student of primary education faculty*

Annotation: *When we talk about education, it cannot be imagined without education. One of the topics that have not lost its relevance not only today but also over the years is the topic of upbringing. In this article, upbringing, which is a part of important education today, its general methods, types, which methods have a positive and significant effect on children according to their character, and the role of education in the formation of their social consciousness is talked about.*

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Understanding of upbringing methods. Purpose, content, form, method, and Concepts such as tools reveal the essence of the educational process. However, another one that has importance in illuminating the essence of education there is also a concept, which is the concept of upbringing methods.

Method of education (Greek "methodos" - way) to the goal of education the way to reach; to the mind, will, feelings, and behavior of the student's methods of influence. When applied to school practice, the methods are methods of influencing the mind, will, feelings, and behavior of students. The problem of improving methods is always there, every educator solves it according to his possibilities, and the process of education is clear based on expressing his private views by the conditions that enrich the general methodology.

There is no positive or negative side to the method, it is known in the process of education it is impossible to evaluate the road as highly effective or ineffective. Evaluating the effectiveness of the method from the point of view of the conditions in which it is used possible Appropriate selection of upbringing methods depends on several factors Appropriate selection of upbringing methods depends on several factors

The goals and tasks of upbringing. The goals and content of upbringing allow choosing the right methods. Whatever the goal is, the means of achieving it must be appropriate.

The content of upbringing is social, which is placed on the formation of a person and consists of the essence of requirements. Do not forget that exactly one task is different, and can be filled with thoughts. Therefore, methods, in general, it is very important to connect not with the content, but with a clear idea.

In the process of upbringing, it is necessary to take into account the age characteristics of students. Age characteristics - anatomical, physiological (physical), and psychological characteristics of a certain age period. Let's say responsibility primary education, secondary and secondary special education, and vocational education can also be formed by students studying in institutions. However, different methods are used for the formation of this quality at each stage.

Upbringing methods in folk pedagogy. Uzbek folk pedagogy embodies all aspects of morality, manners, and education. People's different educational methods and tools are used in pedagogy. These methods and tools are very diverse and in many ways scientifically superior to pedagogy. Therefore, these methods of scientific pedagogy also influenced its formation. It is used in folk pedagogy. The different teaching methods can be summarized as follows.

1. Explain (tell a story, teach).
2. Teaching (getting used to, practicing)
3. Example (giving advice, asking for forgiveness, asking for a compliment, to be an example).
4. advice, instruction (encourage, convince, ask, request, wish, approve, thank, pray, etc.).
5. condemnation and punishment (highlight, condemnation, anger, reprimand, coercion, put, blame, shame, swear, hitting, etc.).

If you pay attention, to the above five general integrity methods. Firstly, the essence of the general process is explained to the child. Children, a pedagogue in cases where he does not understand the essence of things, events, and processes uses the tool of sampling, that is, independent observation of young people. Even in this case, those who do not understand are the advice of adults based on them, they understand the essence of things, events, or processes. Even if the expected result is not achieved, the last resort if they don't want to understand the situation should be used in judgment and punishment. However, judging and

punishing methods according to modern pedagogical ideas proved to be an ineffective measure

Examples of folk pedagogy, upbringing methods, and effects used with certain tools. For example; waiting for a guest, visiting a guest, and various labor processes, (wedding ceremonies, family traditions celebration of birthdays, etc.) are considered special means of education.

Social consciousness-forming methods are methods of influencing students' consciousness and feelings to form their spiritual and moral qualities and worldview. The essence of these methods is that, through them, the students' minds are instilled with the priority social ideas and goals of the Society. Methods of forming social consciousness to help young people understand the meaning of life are used. The explanation is the most important method used in the formation of social consciousness. The task of explanation is to make students grow up cultured and develop a sense of national pride.

Conversation. The personality of the student is ideologically and spiritually and morally. The live speech of the teacher is the most effective method in formation. When choosing a topic for the interview, it is for the students of this class relevance, discussion of spiritual and moral confidence in students taking into account their relationship to the content and the expected result of the conversation need to get. The conversation can be organized on the following topics:

1. Ethical topics (social moral and ethical standards, priority in society existing, social relations, rules of behavior among the community and others);
2. Aesthetic themes (beauty of nature, interpersonal relationships, people beauty);
3. Political topics (internal and foreign policy of the state, world events, international relations, etc.);
4. Topics related to education and knowledge (universe, animals and plants world, electronics, etc.).

Organization of conversations, as well as social work, organization in legal, ecological, economic, and hygienic topics is its own gives positive results.

The story. Students usually like various literature and listen to stories enriched with examples with great interest. They can be told about moral standards, people's past, natural resources, life and courage of heroes, as well as history, literature, and art. Examples of fiction, as well as information

published on the pages of mass media - radio, television, newspapers, and magazines, will be valuable material for students.

Sample. Students need to see all the good moral qualities in the people around them, to learn from them. The role of a teacher as a role model has a great impact, especially on young people. They observe how the teacher behaves in class and life, how he interacts with others, and how he performs his duties. Students imitate the behavior of people close to them. Behavior affects the development of good qualities and sometimes bad qualities in children. Therefore, teachers and parents should be responsible in any case. Wherever they are, they should feel that there are children around them. There should be no difference between the words and actions of adults.

In conclusion, it should be said that not only teachers but also parents should take a responsible approach to child education as the most important factor for his bright future. As one of the famous scholars Abdullah Awlani said; "For us, education is a matter of life or death, salvation, destruction, happiness or disaster." Therefore, we pedagogues have the responsible task of raising, educating, and upbringing the young generation with a broad worldview, loving their nation, patriotic, mature generation. For this purpose, it is possible to achieve positive results by carrying out practical activities based on the age, behavior, and character of children, using the above-mentioned various educational methods.

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